

Finite element simulations of the electro-chemo-mechanical behavior of articular cartilage. Part II: results and discussion

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Abstract

In the present work, the finite element formulation and program presented in part I of this paper, are used to numerically simulate the response of an articular cartilage sample to a combination of chemical and mechanical actions. In the simulations, a sample of articular cartilage, laterally confined, is immersed in a bath of variable chemical composition always assuming the existence of electro-chemical equilibrium at the tissue-bath interface. Nonetheless, inside the tissue, the equilibrium is not attained instantaneously. In fact, the time needed to establish a steady state depends on the problem geometry and on some material properties, namely the percolation and diffusion times associated with Darcy's and Fick's laws, respectively. A good agreement is obtained between the results of the present model and previous experimental data in the case of a homogeneous bath. As another new feature of the model, results are also obtained when the tissue is immersed in a bath which allows each of the sample extremities to experience distinct variations of the chemical composition, which gives a closer insight to the tissue's behavior under a more diverse environment.

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1. Introduction

In this work, a finite element program, whose formulation is based on the model described in part I of this paper, is used to numerically simulate the response of an articular cartilage sample to a combination of chemical and mechanical actions. The finite element formulation follows the framework of the model by Loix *et al.* [1] accounting for the presence of one solid phase and two water compartments (extrafibrillar – EF and intrafibrillar – IF phases). However, as new features of the present formulation: 1) it uses the electro-chemo-mechanical constitutive law defined in [2] and 2) the contribution of the IF phase is considered in a simplified way, not requiring the definition of IF material parameters and functions.

In the simulations, a sample of articular cartilage, laterally confined, is immersed in a bath of variable chemical composition always assuming the existence of electro-chemical equilibrium at the tissue-bath interface. The corresponding chemo-mechanical parameters are obtained from the experimental tests by Eisenberg and Grodzinsky [3] and a good agreement is obtained between the simulated and experimental results. In particular, the shielding effect observed in the experimental results is very well reproduced by the model, which is something that other existing articular cartilage chemo-mechanical models (*e.g.* [4]) and existing finite element software packages based on those models (like FEBio [5]) are not able to replicate since they assume a constant stiffness for the tissue.

As another new feature of the present formulation, 3) numerical results are also obtained when the tissue is immersed in a bath which allows each of the sample extremities to experience distinct variations of the chemical composition. This simulation gives a closer insight to the tissue's behavior under a more diverse environment which is something that other existing models are also not able to provide.

2. Parameter identification

The definition of proper values for the material parameters is conducted by adjusting the mechanical model to actual experimental results obtained by Eisenberg and Grodzinsky [3]. In that work, an extraction of a cylindrical graft of bovine

articular cartilage and bone was performed, followed by several cuts, obtaining a final sample of cartilage from the middle zone with 6.4 mm of diameter and 600 μm of thickness. Posterior confined compression tests were conducted.

Table 1 - Chemical constants.

Species, k	Molar volume, $\hat{v}_k$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Molar mass, $\hat{m}_k$ (kg mol^{-1})	Valence ξ_k
w	18×10^{-6}	0.018	0
Na	2.37×10^{-6}	0.023	+1
Cl	15.42×10^{-6}	0.0355	-1
PG	-	2000	-4500 [2]

The initial volume of the tissue sample described above is $V_0 = 0.0193 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$. Supposing that, initially, 80% of the total volume of the articular tissue is water, the initial total volume of water in the sample may be obtained: $V_w^0 = 0.8 V_0$. However, as mentioned in section 1 of the companion paper, part of the water is contained in the IF space and the remaining in the EF space, being the percentage of water, with respect to the total amount, in the IF and EF phases, 25% and 75%, respectively. In this way, the initial EF water volume is $V_{wE}^0 = 1.1580 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$ and the respective number of moles, considering the water density and the water molar mass (Table 1), is $N_{wE}^0 = 6.4333 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}$. Regarding the PGs, their mass percentage from the total tissue's mass is considered to be 5%, thus resulting in a number of moles $N_{PG} = 5.3075 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}$ and in a volume $V_{PG} = 5.8913 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^3$, considering the PGs' molar mass shown in Table 1 and a tissue density equal to 1.1 g/cm^3 . Since PG molecules are not able to leave the EF space, PGs' mass remains constant.

The bath concentration is initially set to $1000 \text{ mol/m}^3 = 1 \text{ M}$ (practically near to saturation), with its pressure and electrical potential being set to zero (reference values). In a situation of equilibrium between the bath and the tissue, the electro-chemical potentials of the water and ions inside and outside the tissue are equal. In this way, the initial number of moles of the ionic species in the EF phase is $N_{NaE}^0 = 1.28381 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}$ and $N_{ClE}^0 = 1.04497 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}$, from which the initial molar fraction of the PGs is obtained: $x_{PG}^0 = N_{PG} / (N_{wE}^0 + N_{NaE}^0 + N_{ClE}^0 + N_{PG}) = 7.9618 \times 10^{-7}$. Moreover, considering that the initial total volume of the EF phase is given by the contributions of the initial volume of all its constituents (water, ions and PGs), its value is $V_E^0 = 1.2361 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$. Taking into account the valence of the PG molecule (see Table 1), the initial value of the FCD is obtained: $e_{PG}^0 = \xi_{PG} c_{PG}^0 = -193 \text{ moles of charge/(m}^3 \text{ of extrafibrillar water)}$, or, equivalently, $e_{PG}^0 = -0.1125 \text{ mEq of charge/(g of wet tissue)}$, which is within the values of the FCD reported by Maroudas [6].

In a state of equilibrium between the tissue and the surrounding medium, the fictitious bath coincides to the real bath, and thus $\tilde{\pi}_{osm} = \pi_{osm}$ and $\tilde{p}_B = p_B$. Taking additionally the pressure of the real bath as a reference value (formally taking $p_B = 0$), we obtain: $p_E = \pi_{osm}$, and the constitutive equation Eq.(21) in the companion paper, under a uniaxial strain state, becomes:

$$\sigma = -p_E(1 + \alpha_p) + (1 + \alpha_w p_E) E_{sat} \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where the constitutive tensor $\mathbf{E}$ is represented, in a one-dimensional strain state, only by the material parameter E_{sat} and p_E is given by Eq.(A.8) in the companion paper:

$$p_E = RT \left(\sqrt{e_{PG}^2 + 4c^*} - 2c^* \right) \quad (2)$$

where $e_{PG} = \xi_{PG} c_{PG}$ is the tissue FCD and $c^* = c_{NaB} = c_{ClB}$ is the ionic concentration of the bath. In this way, three mechanical parameters have to be defined: α_p , α_w and E_{sat} , the latter being the confined compression modulus at the tissue's saturation state.

The adjustment of the model to the experimental points is performed in two different stages, considering in all cases that the system is under equilibrium:

1. The first stage is performed under a no deformation condition, in which the bath composition is changed, decreasing the concentration from the initial value (chosen to be 1000 mol/m^3) to a given final target concentration;
2. During the second stage, a negative deformation is imposed under a fixed concentration of salt in the bath.

Temperature is considered to be equal to 298 K and pH is considered to be neutral.

Assuming that the collagen fibers (solid phase) and the PG molecules are incompressible, as the contractive uniaxial deformation ($\varepsilon < 0$) is applied, the volume of the EF phase and the FCD value are gradually updated as:

$$V_E = V_E^0 + \varepsilon V_0, \quad (3)$$

and

$$e_{PG} = \xi_{PG} N_{PG} / V_E. \quad (4)$$

After updating e_{PG} using Eq.(4), the water pressure and the corresponding stress are obtained from Eq.(2) and Eq. (1), respectively.

During stage 1, the variation of the salt concentration in the bath, considering a zero deformation, allows to obtain the first mechanical parameter in the mechanical model, α_p , since, during this stage, the stress is only governed by $\sigma = -p_E (1 + \alpha_p)$. Thus, from the initial hypertonic state, the bath concentration is decreased until the target concentration is reached. During this decrease of the bath concentration, a successive increase in the absolute value of the stress, due to the increase of the water pressure, is observed. This trend results from the flow of water towards the inside of the tissue. The lower the final concentration is, the higher is the water pressure, and consequently, the higher is the compressive stress. The value of α_p that most accurately approximates the model to the experimental results is $\alpha_p = -0.95$.

During stage 2, under a constant bath concentration c^* , a negative deformation is applied. With the α_p parameter already defined, the remaining mechanical parameters, α_w and E_{sat} , that determine, for each salt concentration in the bath, the slope of the corresponding stress-strain curve, are obtained. When the salt concentration in the bath is very large, there is a tendency of ionic species to move towards the inside of the tissue, increasing the shielding effect and decreasing the repulsive forces and the compressive stiffness of the tissue. Thus, for the same strain but different bath concentration, a higher compressive stress is observed when the outer concentration is lower, since the repulsive forces are less shielded and the compressive stiffness of the tissue is higher. Moreover, as the contractive strain increases, while maintaining the same chemical conditions, the proteoglycans get closer to each other, increasing the inter repulsive forces. All these aspects are well reproduced by the model, as it may be seen in Fig.1. The curves obtained in Fig.1 are adjusted in order to fit the experimental data [3] and the values of α_w and E_{sat} that minimize the error for all the curves are $5.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ and 250 kPa, respectively.

In order to complete the material constants of the model, the values used for the transport parameters required for the computation of the generalized diffusion matrix components to be used in the finite element simulations, which are retrieved from [1], are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - Transport parameters.

Hydraulic conductivity K_h	Sodium diffusion coefficient D_{NaE}	Chloride diffusion coefficient D_{ClE}	Tortuosity τ
$9.8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m/s}$	$13.3 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	$20.3 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	0.4

3. Finite element simulations

3.1. Initial state and simulation framework

The sample of cartilage considered in section 2 is also considered in the finite element simulations performed in this section. The bath concentration is again initially set to $1000 \text{ mol/m}^3 = 1 \text{ M}$, with its pressure and electrical potential being set to zero (reference values). The tissue sample is also considered to be initially at zero deformation (see Fig.2). Imposing electro-chemical equilibrium between the initial bath and the tissue, all the initial quantities are obtained and their values are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 - Initial values

$V_0 = 0.0193 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$	$V_w^0 = 1.544 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$	$p_E^0 = 2.6413 \times 10^4 \text{ Pa}$	$\phi_w^0 = -2.64283 \times 10^{-3} \text{ V}$
$V_{PG} = 5.8913 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^3$	$V_{wE}^0 = 1.1580 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$	$V_{NaE}^0 = 3.0426 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3$	$V_{ClE}^0 = 1.6113 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^3$
$N_{PG} = 5.3075 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}$	$N_{wE}^0 = 6.4333 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}$	$N_{NaE}^0 = 1.28381 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}$	$N_{ClE}^0 = 1.04497 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}$
$x_{PG}^0 = 7.9618 \times 10^{-7}$	$x_{wE}^0 = 0.9651$	$x_{NaE}^0 = 0.0193$	$x_{ClE}^0 = 0.0157$

From this initial state, alterations are imposed either through changes in the bath concentration (chemical loading) or through the imposition of uniaxial (confined) deformation in the tissue (mechanical loading). During chemical loading, rates of change of the electro-chemical potentials are imposed at the nodes of the extremities of the tissue sample corresponding to constant rate of change of the number of moles of salt in the bath. During mechanical loading, constant rates of displacement are imposed at the nodes of the extremities of the tissue sample.

Fig.1 - Experimental points (symbols) by Eisenberg and Grodzinsky [3] and stress-strain curves obtained by the mechanical constitutive model proposed, while changing the contractive deformation, from zero to a given final strain value, under different bath concentrations c^* from 5 to 1000 mol/m³, with $\alpha_p = -0.95$, $\alpha_w = 5.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ and $E_{sat} = 250 \text{ kPa}$ in Eq.(1).

Fig.2 - A cylindrical tissue sample, with 0.6 mm thickness, is immersed in a bath which is initially homogeneous in both its mechanical properties and chemical composition (concentration A). The specimen is in contact with the bath along the upper and lower surfaces.

The main simulations performed in this work involve four distinct stages, with changes in both the chemical composition of the bath and in the deformation of the tissue (see Fig.2):

1. Stage 1: in the first stage, the bath concentration is decreased from the initial value (1 M NaCl) to a given final target concentration, under zero deformation, in a given time interval t_1 ;
2. Stage 2: during a time interval t_2 , the system is left at rest, so that a new state of equilibrium is reached;
3. Stage 3: in the third stage, under a constant bath solution, a contractive uniaxial strain is imposed in a time interval t_3 ;
4. Stage 4: during a time interval t_4 , the system is again left at rest in order for a new equilibrium to be reached.

The four-stage simulation described above is in part similar to the one conducted in section 2, to obtain the values of the material parameters of the mechanical model. However, in those simulations, long term equilibrium was assumed in all points while, in this simulation, the time variable is included, which allows to study the evolution in time and space of several variables defined within the sample under the combined action of chemical and mechanical "loads", with the equilibrium state being reached during the simulation in the two extra stages 2 and 4.

For the study of the influence of mesh size and time step on the convergence of the method, simulations are conducted with meshes comprising different number of finite elements and different time steps. The corresponding results are described in detail in Appendix A. From these results, it is concluded that the number of elements and the time step that allow a satisfactory convergence of the results, without increasing excessively the computational effort, are respectively equal to 50 elements and 0.1 s.

3.2. Homogeneous bath simulation

In this section, a simulation is conducted (see Fig.2) where, during the first stage, the homogeneous bath concentration is decreased at a constant rate from the initial value of 1000 mol/m^3 to a value of 150 mol/m^3 during 1000 s, under no variation of thickness, followed by a 50 minutes equilibrium stage. In the third stage, a negative 20% deformation is applied during 1000 s, followed by another 50 minutes equilibrium stage.

As the bath concentration decreases during stage 1, an outflow of ions is observed. Therefore, there is a consequent decrease of the sodium and chloride mass contents, m^{NaE} and m^{ClE} , throughout the tissue thickness, as pictured in Fig.3. Nevertheless, it may be seen that such decrease does not occur in a uniform manner over the thickness of the sample, with the impact of the decrease of the bath concentration being first felt in the extremities of the tissue (in contact with the bath), with the posterior progression towards inside the sample.

Fig.3 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the sodium (a) and chloride (b) ionic mass contents, m^{NaE} and m^{ClE} , during stages 1 and 2. The ionic content decreases due to a decrease of the ionic concentration of the bath. The last three curves are practically superimposed which means that steady state is practically reached at $t = 2000 \text{ s}$. The same type of behavior can be observed next in Fig.4 to Fig.6.

Since the total volume during the first two stages of the simulation is the same as the initial one, and recalling that the solid phase is incompressible, the volume of the EF fluid phase must also remain constant. In this way, with the loss of ions in the EF phase, the water mass content, m^{wE} , increases at the end of the second stage, with its profile along the tissue thickness following the trend of the tissue local deformation (see Fig.4). Since in the first 4000 s of the simulation no total deformation is imposed, it may be seen in Fig.4(b) that, at any time, the overall mean strain is zero. However, the local deformation along the thickness of the tissue is not null before steady state is reached. In fact, as the salt concentration decreases in the bath, water enters the specimen from the top and bottom boundaries which consequently expand, while the constraint imposed in the total deformation implies the inverse trend in the middle of the specimen. Overall, integrating the local deformation, the total thickness of the tissue remains constant at any time (see Fig.11).

Fig.5 shows the evolution of the effective PG molar fraction y_{PG} , which is related to the FCD, e_{PG} , by $y_{\text{PG}} \approx \xi_{\text{PG}} C_{\text{PG}} \hat{v}_{\text{W}} = e_{\text{PG}} \hat{v}_{\text{W}}$. The values of y_{PG} vary between $-3.5/-3.6 \times 10^{-3}$, which corresponds to a FCD value $e_{\text{PG}} \approx -190$ moles of charge/ m^3 , within the range of values of FCD referred by Maroudas [6].

The EF water pressure, p_{E} , presents an increase at the end of stage 2 (see Fig.6(a)), being this a consequence of the increase of the water mass content in the EF phase without variation of the volume of the tissue.

The EF electrical potential, ϕ_{E} , is initially practically zero and by the end of the second stage, with the migration of ions towards outside the tissue, it becomes more negative (see Fig.6(b)). In fact, during the refreshment of the bath, the ionic concentrations decrease, both in the bath and in the cartilage, but the change is lower in the cartilage and this implies a decrease of the EF electrical potential.

Fig.4 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the water mass content m^{wE} (a) and of the local tissue deformation ϵ (b), during stages 1 and 2. At time $t = 0$ s, the deformation is homogeneously equal to zero. The last three curves are practically superimposed which means that steady state, with zero deformation, is also practically reached at $t = 2000$ s. Before steady state is reached, the deformation is positive (extension) in the vicinity of the boundaries and negative (contraction) in the center of the specimen; the total thickness of the tissue remains constant at any time, though.

Fig.5 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the proteoglycan effective molar fraction y_{PG} , during stages 1 and 2. The first and the last three curves are practically superimposed, that is, the steady state proteoglycan effective molar fraction is practically equal to the initial value because the initial and steady state water mass contents are very close since the total deformation of the tissue is zero.

In stages 3 and 4, no alterations are imposed in the chemical composition of the bath surrounding the tissue. Thus, changes perceived in the chemical variables are a consequence of the applied deformation. In Fig.7, lower ionic mass contents are observed at the end of the simulation, although such decrease is not as significant as during the first two stages. When applying the contractive deformation, water and dissolved ions are expelled from the tissue. Thus, a decrease in the water mass content is also observed in Fig.8(a), with the consequent decrease of the tissue volume. Once again, the trend of the water mass content curves follows the trend of the deformation profiles (Fig.8(b)). At first, since the imposition of the displacement occurs at the extremities of the tissue, these are the points that experience a larger deformation. As the system evolves towards a new equilibrium, the deformation progresses to the inner points, until a homogeneous deformation is verified along the tissue thickness (see Fig.8(b)).

In contrast to what is verified during the change of the bath chemistry, after the application of the deformation an increase in the negative value of y_{PG} at the end of stage 4 is observed. Due to the decrease in the EF water volume, the PGs concentration is higher and so y_{PG} and the FCD have higher absolute values (see Fig.9).

When the negative deformation is applied, a higher EF water pressure p_E is observed. Moreover, with the exit of more ions, the EF electrical potential decreases once again, as one may verify in Fig.10.

Fig.6 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the EF water pressure p_E (a) and of the EF electrical potential ϕ_E (b), during stages 1 and 2. The increase of water pressure starts at the boundaries through which water infiltrates.

Fig.7 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the sodium (a) and chloride (b) ionic mass contents, m^{NaE} and m^{ClE} , during stages 3 and 4. The ionic content decreases due to the imposed contractive deformation. The last three curves are practically superimposed which means that steady state is practically reached at $t = 6000$ s. The same type of behavior can be observed next in Fig.8 to Fig.10.

Fig.8 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the water mass content m^{wE} (a) and of the local tissue deformation ϵ (b), during stages 3 and 4. The upward motion of the lower boundary and downward motion of the upper boundary are reflected first close to the vicinity of these boundaries, leading to an initial quicker decrease of mass content in these zones.

Fig.9 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the proteoglycan effective molar fraction y_{PG} , during stages 3 and 4. The significant increase in the absolute value of the proteoglycan effective molar fraction is due to the observed strong decrease of the water mass content.

Fig.10 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the EF water pressure p_E (a) and of the EF electrical potential ϕ_E (b), during stages 3 and 4.

The time evolution of the uniform axial stress (Fig.11(a)) shows, during the change of the bath composition (stage 1), a slight increase due to the increase of the water mass content and of the EF water pressure. Once the compression starts at stage 3, with the chemical environment kept constant, the stress suffers a significant increase in absolute value.

In Fig.11(b), it may be observed that the tissue thickness does not change during the first two stages and it decreases, according to the imposed deformation, during the third stage.

Alterations in the period of time during which the bath concentration is changed (stage 1) introduce modifications in the response of the tissue. By making faster the decrease of the ionic content of the bath ($t_1 = 100$ s), the stimulus felt by the tissue is more abrupt, which is reflected in the presence of a more distinct overshoot in the stress underwent by the tissue during stage 1 (see Fig.12(a)). On the contrary, if the alteration in the concentration of ions in the bath is made slower ($t_1 = 5000$ s), the tissue has more time to adapt to the imposed changes, and the overshoot is almost completely absent (see Fig.12(b)).

The hydraulic conductivity (K_h) is a characteristic property of porous tissues which describes the ease of a fluid to flow through the pores (percolation), thus being an indicator of the permeability of the porous medium. This property depends on the medium by itself (*i.e.* pore size, pore distribution and connectivity) but also on the properties of the fluid (*e.g.* density and viscosity) [7]. The higher its value, the higher the permeability is. In order to quantify the influence of the hydraulic conductivity in the behavior of the tissue, its value is changed from the base value 9.8×10^{-12} m/s (see Table 2) to higher (9.8×10^{-11} m/s) and lower (9.8×10^{-13} m/s) values.

Fig.11 - Time evolution of the axial stress in the tissue (a) and of the tissue thickness (b), during the four-stage simulation. After each of the stages involving external chemical (stage 1) and mechanical (stage 3) changes, the stress reaches equilibrium during stages 2 and 4.

Fig.12 - Time evolution of the axial stress underwent by the tissue, considering, for stage 1, a duration of 100 s (a) and 5000 s (b), during the four-stage simulation. After each of the stages involving external chemical (stage 1) and mechanical (stage 3) changes, the stress reaches equilibrium during stages 2 and 4.

As K_h is assigned with successive lower values, water does not flow through the tissue so easily, which means that a higher compressive stress is required to impose the same contractive deformation. This behavior can be verified analyzing the evolution of the stress over time presented in Fig.13(a). On the contrary, when the permeability increases (Fig.13(b)) equilibrium at stage 4 is attained very quickly with almost no overshoot. During the change of the bath composition, differences among the distinct permeability values are not as evident as during the imposition of the deformation. Nevertheless, at the end of the first stage a lower compressive stress is obtained for the lower K_h value, which may be explained due to the fact that water does not flow towards inside the tissue as easily leading to a lower EF water pressure and consequently to a lower compressive stress. Regardless the hydraulic conductivity, at the end of the second and fourth equilibrium stages the final stresses are the same. It should be mentioned that the rapid changes observed in Fig.12(a) and Fig.13(b) have been cross-checked by reducing the time step.

One additional note that should be considered is that the hydraulic conductivity and, consequently, the permeability, depends on the strain applied to the tissue, meaning that under higher deformation states the size of the pores is reduced and the fluid flow becomes more difficult (reduced permeability). In this way, although considered constant in this work,

the hydraulic permeability could have been defined in a way that would depend on the available pore volume for the movement of the fluid inside the tissue. Such dependence was taken into account in [1], based on the Kozeny-Carman equation.

Fig.13 - Time evolution of the axial stress underwent by the tissue, considering a hydraulic conductivity, K_h , equal to 9.8×10^{-13} m/s (a) and equal to 9.8×10^{-11} m/s (b), during the four-stage simulation. After each of the stages involving external chemical (stage 1) and mechanical (stage 3) changes, the stress reaches equilibrium during stages 2 and 4.

The reach of the new equilibrium state after each of the chemical or mechanical changes is not accomplished instantaneously as it is highlighted in each and every one of the figures mentioned above. Instead, the tissue response undergoes a transient period. Such transient time is related with several material properties such as the percolation time related to Darcy's law and the diffusion time related to Fick's law. In the case of absence of electro-chemo-mechanical couplings, the characteristic times of the ionic diffusion and water seepage are given by $\tau_k^{Fick} = 1/(4\pi^2) L^2/D_{kE}^*$ and $\tau^{Darcy} = 1/(4\pi^2) L^2/(E_e k_{EE})$, respectively, with $D_{kE}^* = \tau D_{kE}$, τ the tortuosity factor, L the distance traveled by ions and water, E_e the confined compression modulus and k_{EE} the "short-circuit" permeability.

Analyzing the figures related to the evolution of stress during the stages where the equilibrium is reached (2 and 4), it is possible to retrieve that the equilibrium is attained faster in stage 4 than in stage 2. In Fig.11, the times required to reach the plateau, in stages 2 and 4, are 474 s and 203 s, respectively. This trend is in agreement with the individual times of diffusion and percolation, which, in the present case, are: $\tau_{Na}^{Fick} = 4.285$ s and $\tau^{Darcy} = 3.5658$ s. Since, in the second stage, the system evolution mainly depends on diffusion as a response to the bath chemical alteration, while in the fourth stage the evolution mainly depends on the water flow as a response to the applied deformation, the faster achievement of equilibrium during stage 4 is plausible. However, the characteristic times here presented do not account for the coupled interactions from which the tissue response depends. Of course, the time necessary to reach the equilibrium states depends on the period of time during which the modifications are introduced. The slower the changes in the bath composition or in the imposed deformation are introduced, the faster the equilibrium is reached. In these simulations the same period of time is selected for stages 1 and 3, where the chemical and mechanical actions are imposed. It is observed that a period of time equal to 50 minutes is larger than necessary for the equilibrium to be achieved and, therefore, in the following simulations a period of time equal to 1000 s is considered in stages 2 and 4.

The computational time taken to conduct the four stages of this simulation, with 50 finite elements and a time step of 0.1 s within a total simulation time of 8000s, is around 4 hours using a PC with the following characteristics: Intel Core i7-8750H 2.20 GHz processor and 8 GB of RAM.

3.3. Eisenberg and Grodzinsky simulation

The finite element program is also used to obtain several stress-strain equilibrium points, for different bath concentrations and different contractive deformations, in order to compare with the experimental results by Eisenberg and Grodzinsky [3]. Several simulations similar to the one presented in section 3.2 are then performed imposing, in stage 1, different bath concentrations in the range showed in [3] and imposing, in stage 3, different contractive deformations.

Fig.14 - Stress-strain curves obtained in the finite element simulation using the material parameters specified in section 2. Marked with a × are the steady state points obtained for a given bath concentration and a given contractive deformation. The experimental points by Eisenberg and Grodzinsky [3] are represented with black symbols.

In Fig.14, the stress-strain equilibrium points are represented with a cross (values retrieved at the end of stage 4), along with the respective interpolation curves. The results show that the finite element simulation, using the proposed mechanical model and considering the IF phase as described before, properly simulates the real cartilage behavior captured in these experiments, which is something that Loix *et al.* [1] were not able to simulate.

3.4. Heterogeneous bath simulation

The introduction of the *fictitious bath* concept in the formulation of the constitutive model makes possible to conduct a simulation in which the tissue sample is surrounded by a heterogeneous bath (Fig.15). In such experimental framework, the bath presents a physical horizontal separation which allows each of the sample extremities to experience distinct variations of the salt concentration over time.

To conduct a simulation with a heterogeneous change of the bath chemistry, two different final concentrations are imposed, starting from the initial bath concentration of 1000 mol/m³: in the upper side, the final concentration is set to 250 mol/m³ and, in the lower side, it is set to 150 mol/m³. Once the chemical change is performed at a constant rate during a time equal to 1000 s, with the next 1000 s stage to reach the equilibrium state, a 20% negative deformation is imposed during 1000 s, followed by another 1000 s equilibrium stage (see Fig.15).

Fig.15 - Schematic of a cylindrical tissue sample, with 0.6 mm thickness, immersed in a piecewise heterogeneous bath, with a horizontal physical division, separating the area of concentration A (at the bottom) from the area of concentration B (at the top).

When imposing a change in the chemical content of the bath that is different in the two extremities of the tissue sample, the behavior in the extremity nodes in reaction to the external modifications is predictable, since it is in these

nodes that the changes are imposed. However, the way the response to the stimulus progresses towards inside the tissue sample is not that straight forward.

Looking at Fig.16, profiles similar to those obtained in section 3.2 are shown, being the distribution of the ionic mass contents, at the end of stage 2, now not uniform along the tissue thickness since the heterogeneity of the bath composition contributes to the loss of symmetry in the tissue behavior, which is also perceptible in all the figures that follow. The side of the tissue sample with the higher EF ionic mass contents corresponds to the side in contact with the bath with higher final ionic concentration.

The water mass content and the local deformation are also no longer uniform, neither symmetric, after the new equilibrium state has been reached. In Fig.17(a), after the equilibrium is restored under no variation of thickness, an increase in the water mass content is verified in general along the tissue thickness, since in both sides of the bath there is a significant decrease in the salt concentration. Nevertheless, the water mass content is higher on the lower side of the sample, where a lower final bath concentration is imposed, since it is in this extremity that a higher outflow of ions occurs. Due to this non-uniform behavior of the tissue, although maintaining an overall zero deformation, the local deformation ϵ presents a non-zero value in the upper extremity of the sample (see Fig17(b)).

The proteoglycan effective molar fraction y_{PG} presents the same trend as the deformation, that results from the uneven distribution of water inside the tissue (see Fig.18). The range of y_{PG} values is maintained in comparison to previous simulations.

Fig.16 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the sodium (a) and chloride (b) ionic mass contents, m^{NaE} and m^{ClE} , during stages 1 and 2, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath. The last three curves are practically superimposed which means that steady state is practically reached at $t = 1300$ s. The same type of behavior can be observed next in Fig.17 to Fig.19.

Fig.17 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the water mass content m^{wE} (a) and of the local tissue deformation ϵ (b), during stages 1 and 2, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath.

Fig.18 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the proteoglycan effective molar fraction y_{PG} , during stages 1 and 2, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath.

In Fig.19, the EF water pressure and EF electrical potential profiles, during the first two stages, are presented. The rationale behind the obtained curves follows the same line as described in the case of a homogeneous bath.

Fig.19 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the EF water pressure p_E (a) and of the EF electrical potential ϕ_E (b), during stages 1 and 2, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath.

Fig.20 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the sodium (a) and chloride (b) ionic mass contents, m^{NaE} and m^{ClE} , during stages 3 and 4, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath. The last three curves are practically superimposed which means that steady state is practically reached at $t = 3300$ s. The same type of behavior can be observed next in Fig.21 to Fig.23.

When the contractive deformation is imposed, the evolution of the different variables until equilibrium is reached occurs much like in the case of the homogeneous bath (this is due to the fact that mechano-chemical coupling is not so strong as the chemo-mechanical coupling), the only difference being that in the current simulation the starting state of

stage 3 is not uniform, and thus the results obtained after the imposed deformation (Fig.20 to Fig.23) are not uniform as well.

Fig.21 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the water mass content m^{wE} (a) and of the local tissue deformation ϵ (b), during stages 3 and 4, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath.

Fig.22 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the proteoglycan effective molar fraction y_{PG} , during stages 3 and 4, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath.

Fig.23 - Time evolution of the spatial distribution, along the tissue thickness, of the EF water pressure p_E (a) and of the EF electrical potential ϕ_E (b), during stages 3 and 4, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath.

The time evolution of the stress is shown in Fig.24, where it may be observed that, at the end of stage 4, the compressive stress is a little lower than the one registered in the case of the homogeneous bath (section 3.2). This result

is expected, since one of the baths has the same final concentration as the homogeneous bath (150 mol/m^3), while the second bath has a higher final concentration (250 mol/m^3). In contrast to the case of the homogeneous bath, there are now some points in the tissue in which the sodium mass content is higher, thus implying a higher shielding of the repulsive forces which is translated in a lower tissue compressive stiffness. In this way, the compressive stress required to impose a negative deformation of 20% is lower as well.

Fig.24 - Time evolution of the axial stress in the tissue (a) and of the tissue thickness (b), during the four-stage simulation, for a heterogeneous change in the salt concentration of the bath during the first two stages of the simulation. After each of the stages involving external chemical (stage 1) and mechanical (stage 3) changes, the stress reaches equilibrium during stages 2 and 4.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a finite element program, whose formulation is based on the model described in the companion paper, is developed in a MATLAB environment and used to numerically simulate the response of an articular cartilage sample to a combination of chemical and mechanical actions. The sample of articular cartilage is found immersed in a bath whose chemical composition may be altered, while the tissue-bath interface is considered to steadily remain at electro-chemical equilibrium. However, the equilibrium inside the tissue is not reached instantaneously. In fact, the time required to establish steady state depends on the problem geometry and on several material properties, such as the percolation and diffusion times related to Darcy's and Fick's laws, respectively. Therefore, spatial and temporal profiles are obtained, for several mechanical, chemical and electrical variables defined in the interior of the tissue, due to either isolated or combined actions of chemical (changing of the chemical composition of the external bath) and mechanical (confined compression) loadings. The framework may also simulate tests where the electrical field of the bath is altered but this type of simulations is not reported here.

Using the finite element method, with the new constitutive equation proposed in [2], the experimental stress-strain curves obtained in [3] are successfully modelled. In particular, the observed shielding effect is very well reproduced by the model, which is something that other existing articular cartilage chemo-mechanical models (*e.g.* [4]) and existing finite element software packages based on those models (like FEBio [5]) are not able to replicate, since they assume a constant stiffness for the tissue. The good approximation of the real tissue behavior allows, additionally, to conclude that the simplification regarding the contribution of the IF phase in this model still permits to obtain acceptable outcomes, being this an advantage of the current formulation with respect to the one developed by Loix *et al.* [1] where several material parameters and functions were defined without experimental validation.

The concept of *fictitious* or *equilibrium bath* also allows to obtain spatial and temporal profiles of several variables when the sample is immersed in a heterogeneous bath which gives a closer insight to the tissue mechanical behavior under a more diverse environment. This is something that other existing chemo-mechanical models are not able to provide.

The control of the tissue response to mechanical, chemical and electrical actions is crucial in the improvement of prevention and treatment of its degenerative disease as well as in the development of novel engineered tissues, mimicking the biological and mechanical properties of the tissue, that could be used in regenerative medicine.

Appendix A. Mesh and time convergence analysis

For the study of the influence of mesh size on the convergence of the method, simulations are conducted with 6 meshes comprising different number of finite elements with a successively higher refinement: 6, 12, 25, 50, 100 and 200 elements, all of them using the same integration time Δt equal to 1 s. For each mesh, several variables (both primary and secondary) are extracted at 3 fixed points (point 1 at the extremity of the sample and points 2 and 3 at 100 μm and 300 μm from the extremity, respectively, see Fig.2) in order to study the evolution of their values as a function of the mesh refinement. The evaluation of the variables is performed at the end of the second stage, once the equilibrium is restored, after the change of the bath composition during stage 1 to a chosen final concentration equal to 150 mol/m³.

From Fig.A.1, a convergent trend is perceptible for the considered variables. Even if some curves seem not to tend to an asymptotic value, the numerical values are very close, thus reflecting a good rate of convergence. In fact, it may be observed that the considered mesh refinement has almost no influence on the results, since the maximum observed variation with respect to the values of the finer mesh (with 200 finite elements) is only 0.003%. In this way, the number of elements that is considered to allow a satisfactory convergence of the results, whilst not compromising the computational effort, is equal to 50.

For the study of the influence of the time step on the convergence of the method, simulations are conducted with a mesh of 50 finite elements. Three different time steps $\Delta t = (\text{Time stage})/(\text{Number of steps})$ are tested: 1 s, 0.1 s and 0.01 s. For each time step, spatial profiles of several variables are obtained along the tissue thickness. Analyzing the results presented in Fig.A.2, obtained again at the end of stage 2, a convergent trend is perceptible for the considered variables. The fact that some of the curves, computed with the smallest time step, seem not to be completely flat may be related to the fact that the mesh used in these simulations was not very refined. Since the values of the variables obtained for the two lower time steps (0.1 s and 0.01 s) are, again, very close, a value of $\Delta t = 0.1$ s is considered to reduce the time step influence on the results, without increasing excessively the computational cost.

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Fig.A.1 - Spatial convergence analysis for several variables (electrochemical potentials of extrafibrillar sodium μ_{NaE}^{ec} (a) and water μ_{wE}^{ec} (b), mass contents of extrafibrillar sodium m_{NaE} (c) and water m_{wE} (d), molar fractions of extrafibrillar sodium x_{NaE} (e) and water x_{wE} (f), extrafibrillar water pressure p_E (g) and axial stress σ (h), with values taken at the steady state at end of stage 2 after a change of the bath concentration), at three different spatial positions. Numerical values being so close in each figure reflects the good rate of convergence.

Fig.A.2 - Time convergence analysis for several variables (electrochemical potentials of extrafibrillar sodium μ_{NaE}^{ec} (a) and water μ_{wE}^{ec} (b), mass contents of extrafibrillar sodium m^{NaE} (c) and water m^{wE} (d), molar fractions of extrafibrillar sodium x_{NaE} (e) and water x_{wE} (f), extrafibrillar water pressure p_E (g) and axial stress σ (h), with values taken at the steady state at end of stage 2 after a change of the bath concentration), considering three different time steps: 1s, 0.1s and 0.01s. Numerical values being so close in each figure reflects the good rate of convergence.